

NANOSTRUCTURED HYBRID CARBON NANOTUBE-CERAMICS HETEROSTRUCTURES: MICROSTRUCTURE AND FORMING MECHANISM

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ABSTRACT

The interest in carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as reinforcements for ceramic and ceramic matrix composites has been growing considerably. Herein, we have proposed an original catalytic method based on zirconium (Zr) and boron (B)-contained precursors to synthesize CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ nanostructured composites. Observations show that the in-situ grown CNTs are homogeneously dispersed at each section of the ZrB₂-ZrO₂ matrix. The fragments of CO, CH₄, CO₂ resulting from the ZrB₂ polymeric precursor are identified to be the main carbon sources for CNTs growth. The m-ZrO₂ and t-ZrO₂ are produced at 1100-1300°C, and some ZrO₂ further transforms into ZrB₂ pyrolyzed at 1500°C. There are two kinds of grown CNTs existed in the produced hybrid heterostructures: (i) the worm-like, disordered and incomplete graphitization CNTs; (ii) the long-length and completely graphitized CNTs. The nucleation and growth of CNTs are dominated and controlled by homogeneous vapor-liquid-solid reactions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since Iijima's discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) was published in 1991[1], they have been considered as nanoscale reinforcing/toughening and functional phases for composite materials owing to their outstanding mechanical, thermal and electrical properties [2, 3]. Recently, there has been growing interest and progress in the design and fabrication of CNT macrostructures for effective utilization of their remarkable properties at the macroscale [4-6].

ZrB₂ and HfB₂ based ultra-high temperature ceramics have been regarded as promising candidates for structural applications due to their unique combination of high melting point, good strength, good thermal stability and corrosion resistance [7-10]. However, to date, their brittleness remains a main disadvantage. The incorporation of CNTs into ceramic matrices is expected to significantly enhance toughness and lead to higher strength as well as raising electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity. Several recent studies show that the inclusion of CNTs in ceramic materials, such as Al₂O₃ [10-13], ZrO₂ [14, 15], SiC [16, 17] SiO₂-based glasses and glass ceramics [18-21], is helpful to the mechanical improvement. However, the dispersion effect and mechanical properties for CNTs-ceramics are not as satisfactory as anticipated. Firstly, CNTs have a strong tendency to agglomerate and aggregate due to Van der Waals forces; Secondly, CNTs tend to be easily clustered since they are forced into the spaces among the larger ceramic powder particles during consolidation; Lastly, the high temperatures required to consolidate ceramic matrices are likely to damage or even completely destroy the CNTs.

To address these vital challenges, in-situ grown CNTs on micrometer-scale ceramics is an ideal processing to form CNTs-ceramic multi-scale hybrid structures. The in-situ growth of CNTs is based on the fact that CNTs can grow in nanopores, which are commonly formed in a ceramic body at an intermediate stage of the ceramic formation during thermal sintering or pyrolysis [22, 23]. For polymer-derived ceramics, a metal catalyst is often needed in the liquid precursor, and then the catalyst present in the locations will support the CNTs growth during thermal pyrolysis through grow-

in-place or grow-then-place [24]. Furthermore, the CNTs can grow in a wide range of temperatures from 700 to 1300°C [25] that well fits for sintering or pyrolysis of a ceramic precursor [26, 27]. Thus, it is possible to synthesize in-situ grown CNTs in ceramics in a controlled manner through the choice of suitable growth and pyrolysis environments. The in-situ and localized growth of CNTs could enhance the homogeneous distribution of CNTs in the ceramic matrix with high purity and crystalline quality.

Herein, we report the in-situ growth of CNTs in polymer-derived nanostructured ZrB₂-ZrO₂ ceramics by pyrolyzing zirconium (Zr) and boron (B)-contained precursor in Ar environment. Multifunctional CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ hybrid structures were obtained. The effect of the pyrolyzed temperature, catalyst content and gas fragment on the final structure and morphology of CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ composites were evaluated. The microstructure evolution and formation mechanism of different CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ hybrid structures were also discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Synthesis of nanostructured hybrid ZrB₂-ZrO₂-CNTs composites

The starting Zr-containing precursors and B-containing precursors were used in the present study [28]. The Zr-contained precursor was [(C₄H₈O)Zr(acac)₂]_n with molecular weight about 64870 and a softening point of 170 °C. The B-contained material was 2, 4, 6-tri-methylamino borazine with the chemical formula (NHCH₃)₃B₃N₃H₃ and molecular weight ~600. The component contents of these precursors are shown in Table.1. Then ZrB₂ polymeric precursor solution (with a B/Zr molar ratio of 2) were prepared by dissolving Zr-containing polymeric precursor and B-contained precursor into dimethylbenzene, and the solvent was removed by the reduced pressure distillation technology at 80 °C.

Fig.1 Formation mechanism of CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ nanostructured hybrid heterostructures. (a) Zr- and B-contained precursors with uniformly distributed nickel nitrate; (b) main gases sources produced during decomposition process; (c) dissolution and segregation of nanosized carbon; (d) CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ nanostructured hybrid heterostructures

In the present study, the polymer pyrolysis and catalytic process are used to synthesize CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ hybrid heterostructures consists of following main steps.

(1) Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O was used as a catalyst precursor here. In a typical experiment, 0.5~2g nickel nitrate (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) was added into 100g ZrB₂ polymeric precursor solution and stirred for 1h to make a homogeneous precursor solution. Then the prepared precursor solution was dried and grinded with agate mortars (shown in Fig. 1(a)).

(2) The prepared precursor powders were put into the middle of an alumina ceramic boat and then the ceramic boat was pushed into the middle of an alumina tube, so as to ensure that the polymeric

precursor powders were located at the high-temperature zone of the furnace. The vacuum system of the furnace was evacuated down to -0.1MPa and then filled with Ar to eliminate air in furnace. The thermal pyrolysis route was carried out in the temperature range RT~1000 °C at 5 °C/min and 1000-1500 °C at 2 °C/min, and at 1500 °C holding for 1h. Finally the samples were cooled to room temperature. The Ar flow was maintained at 10ml/min during the pyrolysis process. The fragments of CO, CH₄, CO₂ resulting from the Zr- and B-contained precursors are used to be the main gases sources for CNTs growth (see Fig.1(b) and (c)).

(3) To optimize the processing parameters and understand the formation mechanism of CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ nanostructured hybrid heterostructures, different synthesis temperatures of 1100 °C, 1200 oC, 1300 oC and 1500 oC, different catalyst content of 0.5wt.%, 1wt.% and 2wt.% were used to investigate the morphology evolution of CNTs- ZrO₂-ZrB₂ and growth mechanism of hybrid CNTs-ZrO₂-ZrB₂ nanostructure (Fig.1(d)).

Table.1 Component Contents (wt%) of the Zr-containing and B-Containing Precursors

Component	Zr(%)	O(%)	N(%)	C(%)	B(%)	H(%)
Zr-containing precursor	29.8	26.4	-	37.9	-	5.88
B-containing precursor	-	-	34.41	29.89	27.25	8.34

2.2 Characterization of nanostructured hybrid ZrB₂-ZrO₂-CNTs composites

The microstructural morphology of nanostructured hybrid ZrB₂-ZrO₂-CNTs composites were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 20 kV and a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) attached with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and a high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) at 100 kV. For TEM observations, the powders were dispersed in ethanol solution under ultrasonic treatment for 10 min and then transferred to a copper grid. The phase and composition of hybrid composites were studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD; Rigaku, D/max-rb) with Cu-K radiation. The characterization of carbon nanotubes was analyzed by Raman spectroscopy.

On-line thermogravimetric analysis-mass spectrometry (TG-MS) analyses of the gases evolved from the polymeric precursors during pyrolysis were performed simultaneously using the STA-409CD equipment coupled to a quadruple mass spectrometer QMA-400. Thermogravimetric and derivative thermogravimetric (TG-DTG) analysis were operated from RT to 1600oC with heating rate of 10oC min⁻¹ under a continuous flow of Ar (100 ml min⁻¹). A transfer line, specially designed to connect a vacuum pump in order to optimize the amount of evolved gas, transferred from the TG to the MS. A mass analysis was performed recording different mass fragments (i.e., 16, 18, 28, and 44 amu, respectively corresponding to CH₄, H₂O, CO, and CO₂). The measured outlet gas via mass spectrometric intensities was plotted as a function of temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pyrolysis behavior of the hybrid precursor

The TG-DTG technique was performed to understand the thermal behavior of the ZrB₂ hybrid precursors during the pyrolysis process. The TG-DTG profiles are shown in Fig. 2. The TG results show the following main weight-loss steps. The first one is from 25°C to about 200 °C (8.59% weight loss), and the second one is between 200 and 600 °C (33.24% weight loss). The third one ranged from 600 to 1440°C (total of about 25% weight loss) and very small weight loss is observed between 600 and 1300 °C (about 3.5% weight loss). The above-obtained experimental results show a total ceramic yield of 33.4%. The DTG result represents the maximum peak temperatures at 200, 324, and 1440°C, respectively, which represents the maximum weight loss. The weight loss processes correspond to the volatilization of the residual solvent and partial decomposition of ZrB₂ precursor in lower molecular

weight components (25-600°C), polymer derived ZrO₂ ceramic (600-1300°C) as well as the formation of ZrB₂ (1300-1500°C).

Fig. 2 TG-DTG curves of the catalyst and ZrB₂ polymeric precursors.

To characterize the generative process of the catalyst and polymeric precursors, the phase compositions and crystalline state of the products were characterized using XRD. Fig. 3 shows XRD patterns of pyrolyzied products heat treated at 1500°C. The main phases include m-ZrO₂, t-ZrO₂, ZrB₂ and C (namely CNTs here). Previous investigations [28] revealed that, without additive of catalyst, only t-ZrO₂ could be detected after pyrolyzied at 1100°C. Initial formation of ZrB₂ was observed at 1300 °C, and meanwhile m-ZrO₂ and t-ZrO₂ were also detected. However, zirconia phases disappeared and transformed into ZrB₂ completely while the precursor pyrolyzied at 1500oC (the main reaction: ZrO₂(s) + B₂O₃ (l) + 5C(s) = ZrB₂(s) + 5CO (g)). Therefore, it can be deduced that most C sources will be consumed by the catalyst dots and CNTs can in-situ grow in the pyrolyzied ceramics if there is existence of catalyst, which results in the formation of hybrid CNTs-ZrO₂-ZrB₂ nanostructure instead of pure ZrB₂.

Fig.3 XRD patterns for the polymeric precursors after thermal pyrolysis at 1500°C.

Fig.4 SEM of the ZrB₂ polymeric precursor after pyrolysis with (a) no catalyst additive; (b) nickel nitrate catalyst.

Fig.4 shows the typical SEM images of the hybrid heterostructure with and without additive of catalyst. It can be apparently seen from Fig. 4(a) that pure ZrB₂ grains distribution with size of 1-2μm and no CNTs are detected. As shown in Fig.4 (b), the CNTs have completely surrounded the formed ZrB₂-ZrO₂ and formed complicated hierarchical nanostructures. During the growth of CNTs, the nanostructures can interlink each other and form a network-like structure.

3.2 Microstructure evolution of in-situ grown CNTs

To understand the role of the pyrolysis gases in the synthesis of grown CNTs, the TG-MS analysis (shown in Fig.5) was carried out to study the exhaust gases produced by the decomposition of the ZrB₂ polymeric precursor between 25 to 1500oC. The ion current peaks at m/z 28, 18, 44 and 16 correspond to the components of gases such as CO, H₂O, CO₂ and CH₄, respectively. It follows that the fragments CO, CH₄, CO₂ resulting from the pyrolysis of ZrB₂ polymeric precursor are identified to the main carbon sources for CNTs growth. One can derive that main chemical reactions during pyrolysis between carbon sources and catalyst are as follows [29]:

Fig.5 TG-MS of polymeric precursor during pyrolysis (m/z=44 (CO₂); m/z=28 (CO); m/z=18 (H₂O); m/z=16(CH₄))

As these chemical processes suggest, carbon could directly be produced (reactions (2) and (3)) or produced afterward as end products of reactions (3) and (4). According to the TG-MS analysis, the CO is an important carbon source for the CNTs growth via CO disproportionation. CO disproportionate catalytically on the surface of the catalyst particles by the boudouard reaction (1), leading to the nucleation and growth of CNTs [30]. The CH₄ is secondary carbon source which could occur through the reaction (2), (3), and (4). The CO₂ plays at least three important roles in the CNTs synthesis: (i) CO₂ acts as a reaction agent to remove the amorphous carbon, which would keep the catalyst active and increase the length and yield of CNTs [31]. (ii)CO₂ can be dissociated on the surface of the catalyst clusters and reacts with other molecules and radicals, resulting in intermediates that can be more effective for the CNT growth. (iii) CO₂ reacts with CH₄ to supply certain amount of carbon source for growth of CNTs. Additionally, the intermediate product H₂ might help to generate methane (reaction (3) and (4)), and its presence in the reaction also keeps the metallic catalyst particle from being oxidized.

Fig.6 Microstructural morphology of the in situ-grown CNTs pyrolyzed at different temperature (a) 1100°C; (b) 1200 °C; (c) 1300°C and (d) 1500°C.

Fig.6 show the typical morphology of the in-situ grown CNTs at different pyrolysis temperature. From Fig.6 (a), it can be seen that only short-length CNTs can be detected at 1100°C. As shown in Fig.6 (b), some CNTs grew readily at 1200°C, and many worm-like CNTs existed in the produced structure. However, when thermally treated at 1300°C and 1400°C, the CNTs became longer in growing direction with a diameter of 80-100 nm (as in Fig.6(c) and (d)). Though the detectable conversion for CH₄ at temperature higher than 500°C [32], as indicated in reaction (1), the formation of CNTs was strongly affected by the matching between decomposition rate and the transfer/diffusion rate of the carbon formed. Due to the low content of the produced CH₄ (as shown in Fig.5), it is difficult for carbon diffusion through the catalyst and the nucleation and formation of graphitic layers at 1100°C. Reaction (2) seems to be inclinedly produced, but reaction (3) actually occurred more easily, which is attributed to the high H₂O content during pyrolysis by TG-MS analysis and the lowest enthalpy. Therefore this boudouard reaction (reaction2) could be easily blocked, because most CO was consumed and the carbon diffusion and nucleation cannot keep up with the carbon deposition. With the increase of temperature (i.e., at 1300 and 1500 °C), increasing amount of carbon deposited and diffused into catalyst, the balance between dissociation, diffusion and segregation was stabilized, the CNTs growth increased.

Fig. 7(a)-(c) shows TEM images of the grown worm-like CNTs, which have curved and tubular structures with diameters of about 50 nm (Fig.7(b)). The high resolution TEM (Fig.7(a)) revealed that the worm-like CNTs are disordered and incomplete graphitization. The SAED also showed the CNTs had a typical microcrystal-ring structure (as in Fig.7(c)). Comparatively, the produced CNTs in Fig.7(d)-(f) are extraordinary smooth with a bamboo-like structure. The high-resolution TEM images further reveal that the grown CNTs are completely graphitized and the lattice fringes distributed uniformly. The corresponding SAED pattern in Fig. 7(f) illustrates a relatively clear ring corresponding to C (100), (105), (110), (200), (211), (217), and (301). Enlargement of the walls of the CNT shows the value of the intershell spacing is 0.357 nm along <0001> direction and is really the fringes of the C (002) layers.

Fig.7 TEM images of produced carbon nanotubes: (a) high resolution TEM of worm-like CNTs (b) typical TEM of a CNT with a diameter of about 50 nm; (c) SAED of the CNT diffraction ring in Fig.7(a); (d) high resolution TEM of bamboo-like CNTs; (e) typical TEM of a CNT with the diameter of 100 nm; (f) SAED of CNT diffraction ring in Fig.7(d).

3.4 Microstructure evolution of in-situ grown CNTs

One of the most accepted growth models is the vapor-solid-solid (VSS) model that derives from the vapor-liquid-solid model for growth of CNTs. The excessive carbon from the decomposition of the hydrocarbon gases (i.e., CO, CH₄ and CO₂) precipitates on the surface of the catalyst, diffuses into the catalyst, and nucleates the CNTs at the edges of the catalyst.

Fig.8 TEM of the grown bamboo-like CNTs produced at 1500°C: (a) low magnification; (b) high magnification showing a typical tip-growth model.

For catalysts on a substrate, the generally accepted tip-growth mechanism where the CNTs lifts the catalyst from the substrate during the growth, as the CNTs nucleates and grows below the catalyst.

The typical tip-growth direction and morphology are evidenced in Fig.8(a) and (b).The carbon atoms produced from hydrocarbon gases dissolve into the nickel particle and diffuse either through the bulk of the metal or along the metal surface. It is generally accepted that carbon diffusion is the rate limiting step during CNTs growth, since the activation energy for carbon diffusion is in reasonable agreement with the energy needed for CNTs formation, as shown by experimental and theoretical approaches [33, 34].

3.4 In-situ grown CNTs containing ZrB_2 - ZrO_2

The nitrate-citric acid reaction has been considered to be a convenient way to prepare oxide nanoparticles at a relative lower temperature [35]. With the increasing of $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$ introduction, the CNTs yield in the composites increases and forms a network distribution. Obviously, the massive carbon atoms accelerate CNT growth as more catalyst nanoparticles granulate together and compete with each other.

The formation of nucleation site from the catalyst source occurs in several stages. At about 400°C, the nickel nitrate thermal decomposes to form NiOx before being transformed to Ni subsequently, as per the following reactions [36]:

Fig.9 SEM images of CNTs- ZrB_2 - ZrO_2 composite powders pyrolyzed at 1500°C with different content of catalyst additive (left: low magnification; right: high magnification): (a) 0.5wt.%; (b) 1wt.%;(c) 2wt.% and (d) typical TEM of CNTs containing ZrB_2 - ZrO_2 ceramic grains.

Fig.9 (a)-(c) shows the CNTs- ZrB_2 - ZrO_2 hybrid morphology pyrolyzed at 1500 °C using Zr-contained precursors and B-contained precursors with different $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$ additive. When $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ content increases from 0.5wt% (Fig. 9(a)) to 2wt% (Fig. 9(c)), the length and the surface density of CNTs increase, while the diameter of CNTs does not change much. Fig.9 (d) is a typical TEM image of grown CNTs containing ZrB_2 - ZrO_2 ceramic grains (as indicated by the blue arrows), showing that the grain size of ZrB_2 - ZrO_2 ceramic ranges from 20 to 80nm. According to the result of Fig.2 and Fig.3, most m- ZrO_2 and t- ZrO_2 were produced at 1100-1300oC, however, some ZrO_2 will transform into ZrB_2 while pyrolyzed at 1500°C. Therefore, the CNTs in-situ grown and distributed in the pyrolyzed ceramics, which results in the formation of hybrid CNTs- ZrO_2 - ZrB_2

nanostructure.

Fig.10 Microstructure of abnormal CNTs growth after pyrolysis at 1500°C: (a) hybrid CNTs with large-size and small-size diameter at low magnification; (b) morphology at high magnification in Fig.6(a); (c) a few amount of short worm-like CNTs distributed in large-size CNTs;(d) large amount of short worm-like CNTs.

It is noticeable that some short and worm-like CNTs are detected with a diameter of about 10nm, which is attributed to the competitive growth on the site of carbon source (as indicated by the red arrows). Compared with traditional synthesis processing, such as CVD, the growth of CNTs could be controlled through designed temperature, stale feeding gases, and catalysts. The catalytic and thermal pyrolysis processing was likely to produce CNTs-based heterostructures. A considerable quantity of peculiar CNTs morphology was also detected after thermal pyrolysis (as shown in Fig.10(a)-(d)). This is highly possible attributed to the following influence factors: (i) high temperature sintering of Ni catalyst particle would enhance the Ni atom diffusion and grain growth, which is helpful to the formation of CNTs with large-size diameter during 1300-1500°C. (ii) the activation energy of catalyst increased with temperature, therefore most of carbon atom could directly diffuse to crystal face of CNTs and promote the CNTs grow with large diameter. (iii) the CO disproportionation is relatively slower than thermal decomposition of CH₄ [37]. Compared with CO, CH₄ usually produces CNTs with larger diameters and a broad diameter distribution, as evidenced by the absorption and photoluminescence characterization results [37, 38].

4 CONCLUSIONS

We present a catalyst-controlling in-situ growth of CNTs in polymer-derived nanostructured ZrB₂-ZrO₂ heterostructures. Multifunctional nanostructured CNTs-ZrB₂-ZrO₂ hybrid structures were prepared in Ar environment. The pyrolysis behavior, microstructure evolution, and formation mechanism of hybrid heterostructures were discussed. The fragments of CO, CH₄, CO₂ resulting from the pyrolysis of ZrB₂ polymeric precursor are identified to be the main carbon sources for CNTs growth. There are two kinds of grown CNTs existed in the produced hybrid heterostructures: (i) the short-length and worm-like CNTs that are disordered and incomplete graphitization; (ii) the long-length and completely graphitized CNTs. The vapor-liquid-solid and tip-growth mechanism for grown CNTs are further proposed and analyzed here. Overall, the current investigation provides an innovative and a cheap approach of synthesizing nanostructured ZrB₂-based ultra-high temperature ceramics and new insights into the growth mechanism of CNTs.

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